

THE WAYS TO LEARN ENGLISH EFFECTIVELY

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Abstract. *This article discusses about the difficulties to learn English and the ways to make it easier to learn. It relies on some practical ways which helped most to master the language. Moreover, it recommends some platforms where people can get the knowledge of English free.*

Key words: *comprehension, skill, goal, motivation, You Tube, Tandem, podcasts, special notebook.*

СПОСОБЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассказывается о трудностях изучения английского языка и о том, как облегчить его изучение. Он опирается на некоторые практические способы, которые больше всего помогли освоить язык. Более того, он рекомендует несколько платформ, где люди могут бесплатно изучать английский язык.*

Ключевые слова: *понимание, умение, цель, мотивация, You Tube, Тандем, подкасты, специальный блокнот.*

INTRODUCTION

It can be difficult for adults to start learning English from scratch, because you need to again feel like a student who does not yet know simple words and basic rules. However, there is nothing shameful in the fact that you start learning a language as an adult, quite the contrary: the thirst for knowledge always inspires respect. According to statistics from our school, people enroll in the first stage at 20, 50 and 80 years old. Moreover, they not only begin to master the language, but reach high levels.

Many people ask the question: “What is the best way to start learning English?” First, you should choose a learning method that is convenient for you: in a group, individually with a teacher, or on your own. You can read about the pros and cons of each of them in the article “4 best ways to learn English.”

The best option for those who are going to learn a language from scratch is classes with a teacher. You need a mentor who can explain how the language works and help you build a foundation of your knowledge. The teacher will help you:

- start speaking English;
- practice correct pronunciation;
- understand grammar;

Additional skill of listening comprehension of English speech.

If you don't have the opportunity to study with a teacher, try to learn English on your own. Next, we'll look at how to do this effectively.

General tips: how to learn English from scratch

Some tips on how to better organize your studies so that your efforts are not wasted:

Exercise at least 2-3 times a week for 1 hour

Ideally, you should devote at least 20-30 minutes to English every day. However, if you want to have a weekend, study every other day for 40-60 minutes.

Work on speech skills

Write short texts, read simple articles and news, listen to podcasts for beginners, and find someone to talk to practice your speaking skills. Immediately apply the acquired knowledge in practice

Simple cramming will not give the desired effect: knowledge will fly out of your head if you do not use it. If you have learned a dozen words, make up a short story using this vocabulary, and then say it out loud. We have studied the Past Simple - write a short text using this tense.

The main mistake beginners make is trying to take as many materials as possible and work with them all at the same time. As a result, language learning will turn out to be unsystematic, you will get confused in the abundance of information and will not see progress.

How to start learning English from scratch on your own

We have compiled a selection from which you will learn where to start learning English and how to do it correctly.

1. Learn the rules of reading English

This is a basic piece of knowledge that will help you learn to read English and pronounce sounds and words correctly.

How to understand English transcription?

2. Check how words are pronounced

Repeat what has been covered

Even if you think that you have memorized the words on the topic “Weather”, return to them in a month - repeating what you have covered is never superfluous. In our blog we have already written about how to repeat so as not to forget anything. Familiarize yourself with the techniques and try to put them into practice.

Even if you know the rules of reading, when learning new words, check how they are pronounced correctly. English words are not read the way they are written, and some of them refuse to follow any reading rules at all. We recommend checking the pronunciation of each new word in an online dictionary, such as Cambridge Dictionary or Dictionary.com.

3. Start building your vocabulary

Use visual dictionaries, for example, use the English picture dictionary resource. Bright pictures, voiced by native speakers and translation into Russian will make it easier for you to learn and memorize new vocabulary.

Listen to podcasts at your level

Accustom yourself to the sound of foreign speech, for example, start with short podcasts. You can find simple audio recordings with translation into Russian on the free British Council resource or the paid Podcast in English.

When learning a language on your own, there is another disadvantage - the lack of control: you will not notice your mistakes and correct them. Therefore, we recommend that you consider taking classes with a teacher at least at the beginning of your journey. The teacher will let you

decide on the push and help you choose the right direction of movement - exactly what a beginner needs.

According to statistics, English today is the native language of more than 370 million people. English, along with Chinese and Spanish, is consistently in the top three in terms of the number of speakers. No matter what country in the world we go to, knowledge of spoken English will definitely not be superfluous. For employees of many facilities located in tourist areas, one of the main requirements when hiring is at least a minimum proficiency in English. It is for all of the above reasons that the question of how to learn English on your own has been relevant for many years. And what kind of programs and methods for teaching a foreign language have not been invented today.

Many methods promise to achieve simply scientific results in a short time. To begin with, there is a program that allows you to speak English for 3 months without being Queen Elizabeth.

Of course, there are no miracles when learning a foreign language, and you are unlikely to learn how to explain to an American how to get to the metro in the first lesson. There are people who speak English a little easier than those who are infected. But do your best to train everyone.

Whether you learn English on your own or with a tutor is, of course, up to you. Each person is individual. Some people find it difficult to force themselves to study at home. Such people, no matter whether it comes to sports or a foreign language, choose a mentor for themselves. Some students simply do not have the time or opportunity to attend English courses. But, thanks to the Internet, today foreign languages have become accessible to everyone.

I want to learn English language! Goals and motivation

Let's say you decide to learn English on your own. You should start by defining your goals and finding motivation.

Children at school are often reluctant to learn English words and are nervous when they are forced to memorize grammar, precisely because they do not understand why they need all this in the first place. But if schoolchildren can still be motivated by exams and grades, then with adults, unless, of course, we are talking about the Faculty of Linguistics, such a trick is unlikely to work. We need to understand why we are learning a language. Then the process will go much faster and easier.

So, as a rule, an adult enrolls in a foreign language course or decides to learn English on his own for the following reasons:

- trips;
- work in an international company;
- moving for permanent residence to an English-speaking country.

The choice of teaching aids and the duration of study depend on the purpose for which you study a foreign language. For those who are simply going on a trip to a Russian-speaking country, sometimes it is enough to take a phrasebook with them. If you have time before your trip, you can buy an English tutorial. In fact, few people master such manuals from cover to cover, but the most necessary conversational phrases in everyday life can be learned on your own.

Most of us find ourselves in typical situations when traveling: visiting museums and souvenir shops, buying food in a supermarket, walking along the streets, placing an order in a

restaurant, traveling in a taxi and purchasing plane or train tickets. It is on all of the above topics that it is highly advisable to learn vocabulary before traveling abroad.

However, if you consider yourself an avid traveler and intend to travel halfway around the world, then you need to learn English at least to the B1 (Intermediate) level. This will help you make more new friends while traveling and expand your horizons by communicating with foreigners.

Resources to learn English

If we had to choose five resources without which you will find it difficult to learn English, we would choose these five.

1. Individual lessons

The only way that really works for learning a language is to practice speaking. Spoken English is the hardest skill to develop on your own. This also seems to be the most nerve-wracking task, which is why many students leave it for last. This is a huge mistake! If you want to speak English confidently, speaking practice should be your top priority.

Individual lessons are the most effective way to get quality speaking practice. Work with a personal tutor and you'll have a safe place to practice speaking English. You can make mistakes and ask questions, and you won't have to worry if you feel confused. With no other classmates to worry about, the lesson will focus entirely on the skills that matter most to you. You will be amazed at how productive those few hours a week are!

Luckily, one-on-one training has never been more accessible. Preply has thousands of qualified English tutors you can choose from based on price, rating, availability, and specialty. Browse our list of English tutors to find the perfect teacher for your needs.

2. Special notebook

The Internet has revolutionized language education. Interactive apps and online exercises have great value, but don't forget the basic teaching methods we've relied on for hundreds of years.

Numerous experiments have shown that writing out new information by hand is an extremely powerful tool for transferring it into your long-term memory. A 2014 study from Princeton University found that students who took notes using paper and pen retained significantly more than students who typed. The handwriting group was particularly good at remembering large concepts.

Take some advice from scientists and write down at least some of your notes the old fashioned way. You might find it useful to keep a small notepad in your pocket to quickly jot down new words you learn on the go, whether it's for everyday English conversations or looking up words in a language learning app. Some students prefer to have one large notebook with all of their new language skills, from handwritten conjugation charts to example sentences and lesson notes. In any case, it's worth experimenting with notepads when learning English. Don't underestimate the powerful effect of writing new information by hand!

3. You Tube

Now that most cat videos have migrated to TikTok, it's becoming increasingly clear: YouTube is a great platform for learning. In many ways, it feels like the website was made for language learners! You can watch videos at reduced speed or with subtitles. These options are

ideal for those who have difficulty communicating with native speakers who speak quickly. Plus, there is a wealth of content created specifically for ESL learners.

Some channels, like JenniferESL, offer a whole course of video lessons on YouTube. Others, like Canadian Bob, teach users about common situations in English that are too unusual to be mentioned in textbooks, such as "going to the hardware store." In short, there is a lot of extremely user-friendly and professional content available for free, and you would be upset if you missed out on it. Many of the most popular English-speaking YouTubers even host regular live interactive lessons.

Here's a recent lesson on vocabulary building by veteran Preply teacher Mike P. The gap between the best ESL YouTube channels and online English courses is getting smaller all the time!

4. Language exchange websites

Tandem language exchange 2020

If you want to speak English as quickly as possible, speaking practice should be your priority from the very beginning. If you don't live near native English speakers and can't afford as many private lessons as you'd like, there are still ways to get those precious hours of conversation!

Try online language exchange. Make friends with a native English speaker who wants to learn your native language and exchange language skills. Spend some time chatting in English (to practice!), and some time chatting in your native language (so the other person can practice too). It may take some time to find the balance between the roles of student and teacher, but it is worth it and will help with discipline. A good language exchange can be a very effective and fun way to learn.

Language exchanges are another aspect of learning English that has become much easier with the advent of the Internet!

5. Podcasts

all ears english podcast

These days there are podcasts about almost everything, every topic and hobby. Like YouTube, there is a wide selection of free podcasts for learning English. Many of the best offer full transcripts so you can read what you hear and develop your ear for English pronunciation. The main benefit of studying with podcasts is that they fit into parts of your day that you might not use for studying.

CONCLUSION

People find the language learning process difficult when they start it to learn themselves. However, in this technology age several platforms, gadgets and recourses offer opportunities to master any language by providing the chance to talk to native speakers in person to put the learners' theoretical knowledge into practice.

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